

Additional file 7: Table S4. Oligonucleotides.

Name	Use	Sequence
sgRNA1/2f	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	GCGGCCCGGGTTCGATTCCCGGCCGAT GCAGATCAAGTACGTGTGGCATGGTTTT AGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAG
sgRNA1/2r	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	ACAGCGGCTGGAAGCCGGCGTGCACCA GCCGGGAATCGAACCC
sgRNA2/3f	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	CGCCGGCTTCCAGCCGCTGTGTTTTAGA GCTAGAAATAGCAAG
sgRNA2/3r	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	AACAGTCTGAGCTCGGCCCTGCACCA GCCGGGAATCGAACCC
sgRNA3/4f	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	GGGGCCGAGCTCAGACTGTTGTTTTAGA GCTAGAAATAGCAAG
sgRNA3/4r	<i>Osi8</i> sgRNA vector	ATTTAACTTGCTATTTCTAGCTCTAAAA CGACCCAGCCGGAATGTCCTTGCACC AGCCGGGAATCGAACCC
HA1f	<i>Osi8</i> donor vector	CGCCGAATTCGGATCAATAGCCTA
HA1r	<i>Osi8</i> donor vector	GCGGCCGCGGGACTGTGCTGGGTA
HA2f	<i>Osi8</i> donor vector	GGCCGCTCTTCGTATGCTCGCATTTGCA TTTGAA
HA2r	<i>Osi8</i> donor vector	GCGCGCTCTTCGGACTACATGCCTCTGC CTCTGGT
Osi8 ¹ f	<i>Osi8</i> ¹ validation	AATTCATCAAGTACGTGTGGCAT
Osi8 ¹ r	<i>Osi8</i> ¹ validation	CTCGAGCAGGCTCTTGGCGCTGCC
Osi8 ¹ -HA1f	<i>Osi8</i> ¹ validation (control)	CGCCGAATTCGGATCAATAGCCTA
Osi8 ¹ -HA1r	<i>Osi8</i> ¹ validation (control)	GCGGCCGCGGGACTGTGCTGGGTA
Osi8promf	<i>Osi8-Gal4</i>	GGATCCTCAAAGACGAAAACCTGG
Osi8promr	<i>Osi8-Gal4</i>	GAATTCCTTTGGGTGCTCAACTGA
Osi8f	<i>UAS-Osi8</i>	GAATTCAGAAGCGCCCGGCGTCAT
Osi8r	<i>UAS-Osi8</i>	TCTAGACGGGTAGCAGAATTTACT
Osi8-SSf	<i>UAS-SS:EGFP:Osi8</i>	GAATTCGCCAGCTACCAGCATCAG
Osi8r	<i>UAS-SS:EGFP:Osi8</i>	TCTAGATCACAGGCTCTTGGCGCT
GstE4f	RNA FISH probe	TATCGCTATACGGCCTGGAC
GstE4r	RNA FISH probe	CCTCAAGAGCTCCACGAACT
Tsp47Ff	RNA FISH probe	GTTCTTGCGGTCCGAGTTTA
Tsp47Fr	RNA FISH probe	GATCAGGATGATGGCGTTCT
dvef	RNA FISH probe	ACACCGAGGACTTGAACACC

dver	RNA FISH probe	GGAGGGGCTCTCAAATAAGG
CG13285f	RNA FISH probe	CCGCCGTATTCAGATTGTTT
CG13285r	RNA FISH probe	GATTCCGCTGACCCTGATAA
CG34456f	RNA FISH probe	CAACAAGTGGCTATATAAGATTGCAG
CG34456r	RNA FISH probe	TTTGTTTTGATAAATTGAAAGAAAGC
CG14153f	RNA FISH probe	GCACTTATGCCCCTGATGAT
CG14153r	RNA FISH probe	AATGGCTCTTGAGGGGATTT
a10f	RNA FISH probe	ATCGATTGAAAATGGGACA
a10r	RNA FISH probe	TTGGCCTTGGACTTCATCTC
a5f	RNA FISH probe	AGCCAGGATAACGACGAGAA
a5r	RNA FISH probe	CCCATTGCATTAGCAATCCT
CG10357f	RNA FISH probe	ACATGCCGCTTTGCTAGACT
CG10357r	RNA FISH probe	GGGGTTTAACCGCCATCTAT
Jhedupf	RNA FISH probe	AGCTGTTGCTGTCGGAGATT
Jhedupr	RNA FISH probe	TTTTGGATCTCCTCCGAATG
Obp59af	RNA FISH probe	CAACGATGGAGGTCAGTGTG
Obp59ar	RNA FISH probe	CACAAACCATTCAACGCAAC